

University Marine Energy Research Community

2023 Conference

4-6 October | Durham, NH, USA

Quantifying Avoidance and Probabilities of Fish-Turbine Encounters and Impacts Using an Agent-Based Model

Jezella I. Peraza*, John K. Horne

University of Washington, 1122 NE Boat Street, Seattle, WA, 98105, USA

Abstract

Quantifying risks associated with fish and tidal turbine interactions is often impeded by lack of data on fish behavior in dynamic environments. Agent-based models incorporate environmental and behavioral factors that can track individual animal trajectories and interactions. Our approach was to construct an agent-based, encounter-impact model that addresses current knowledge gaps when quantifying risk estimates. The model integrates fish avoidance, collisions, and hydrodynamics to estimate probabilities of fish approaching and potentially interacting with a turbine. The model includes Pacific herring (*Clupea pallasii*) behavior by assigning rules and physiological constraints based on empirical studies and biological reasoning. Probabilities are estimated by tracking fish duration in sequential model volumes. Impact probabilities are estimated by tabulating fish-turbine interactions with the lower portion of the turbine base as collision and the upper section of the turbine as entry, where the probability of a blade strike is assigned using literature values. If fish collide with the lower section of the turbine followed by interaction with the upper section, then a collision and blade strike is possible. The sum of individuals in each model component is used to estimate population probabilities of occurrence within model components and overall population impacts. This agent-based, encounter-impact model can be used to investigate fish behavior and assess risk by including empirically-based behavioral patterns, environmental conditions, and turbine characteristics.

Keywords: agent-based model; collision risk, encounter, fish, hydrokinetic turbines

1. Introduction

Efforts to quantify risks associated with fish and tidal turbine interactions often lack data on fish behavior in changing environmental conditions, particularly device avoidance, collision, and blade strike rates. Interactions of fish with stationary and rotating components of tidal energy devices potentially affect passage and survival of migratory fish [1]. Incomplete empirical data on fish-turbine interactions necessitates the use of simulation models to estimate probabilities of animal-device encounters. Model results can be used to quantify uncertainties of animal-turbine interactions [2] and aid development of regulatory monitoring policies for Marine Renewable Energy (MRE) sites [3].

Agent-based simulation models can be used to analyze insufficient data or understudied factors such as device avoidance that influence impacts of tidal turbines on aquatic animals. Agent-based models (ABMs) are a flexible and accessible tool that can incorporate environmental and behavioral factors within the structure of the ABM [4].

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: jezper@uw.edu

ABMs are initialized with behavioral rules (e.g., aggregation, avoidance) and parameter values formulated from field observations, existing datasets, or published values [4]. Populations are represented using individual agents (i.e., organisms) that contain unique traits [5]. The model's structure allows agents to perceive and respond to their environment, other agents, and obstacles [6]. ABMs can also be used to generate data that are used to complement or extend empirical datasets when empirical data are limited or unavailable [7].

At this time, there is no single model that includes all relevant aspects of animal encounters and interactions with MRE devices: aggregative behavior, active and passive avoidance, and collisions and blade strikes with turbines. Empirical/statistical models do not incorporate fish avoidance or suitable behavioral traits (e.g., [8], [9]). ABMs include behaviors that determine individual and group trajectories in response to animal distributions, environmental conditions, and blade strikes [2], but do not incorporate avoidance [10] or collision with a turbine base.

To increase accuracy of fish-device interaction estimates, an agent-based model should include all factors influencing aquatic animal encounters with MRE devices. Our three-dimensional model integrates fish active and passive avoidance, impacts with axial and cross-flow stationary and mobile structures, and fluctuating hydrodynamic conditions to estimate probabilities of fish approaching and potentially interacting with a tidal turbine. This model is designed to be generic and adaptable to species, device types, and locations of interest.

2. Methods

2.1. Agent-based encounter-impact model description

The agent-based, encounter-impact model includes agent characteristics and sequential steps in the approach and interaction with a tidal turbine. Agents are assigned behavioral traits such as avoidance behaviors and social interactions as their response to turbines is influenced by tidal flow and length-based swimming capability (Fig. 1) [11]. Sequential stages include an approach, being entrained, and then interacting with one or more components of the tidal turbine (Fig. 2). The approach phase of the model includes agent entry to the model domain and zone of influence. The zone of influence is the reaction distance between a fish and turbine and is arbitrarily set to Shen *et al.*'s [12] 140 m upstream from a device regardless of turbine type or tidal flow speed. The entrainment phase occurs within the spatial volume adjacent to a turbine, with the volume size proportional to turbine size. The impact phase of the model occurs at the tidal device and includes potential collisions with the device structure and/or blade strikes. All phases of the model include active and passive avoidance. Full details of the encounter-impact model components are found in Peraza & Horne [13].

Fig. 1. Agent characteristics are divided into behavioral and environmental components. Behavioral characteristics include turbine detection and fish aggregation. Environmental characteristics include tidal flow.

Fig. 2 A schematic of the encounter-impact model. On the left-hand side of the figure, the model is divided into approach, entrainment, and impact phases. The center of the figure details model components. The right-hand side of the figure lists literature used as parameter sources attributed to corresponding model components.

2.2. Empirical data description and tidal turbine dimensions

Data used to extract parameters for the model were collected in 2011 in Admiralty Inlet, Puget Sound, WA at a site for potential deployment of two Open Hydro (<https://www.emec.org.uk/about-us/our-tidal-clients/open-hydro/>) turbines. Tidal velocity data were collected for 12 minutes every two hours using a bottom-deployed 1MHz Nortek AWAC acoustic doppler current profiler (ADCP) [14]. Fish community composition and length data were collected from a Marinovich midwater trawl catches deployed from a mobile surface vessel. Among captured species, Pacific herring (*Clupea pallasii*) represented 32% of the total catch by number. The average length of Pacific herring caught in the midwater trawl was 15.5 cm. Additional survey details can be found in Horne *et al.* [16].

For this study, both axial and cross-flow tidal turbines are modeled in simulations. Tidal turbine dimensions are based on an axial-flow Verdant Power Kinetic Hydropower System (KHPS) [15] (Fig. 3a) and a cross-flow Ocean Renewable Power Company (ORPC) TidGen Power System [12] (Fig. 3b). The KHPS has a rotor-swept area of 5 m in diameter, is approximately 5 m wide, and 10 m high, defining an area of 5 m by 5 m by 10 m. The TidGen device is 31.2 m long, 15.2 m wide, and 9.5 m high, defining an area of 30 m by 15 m by 10 m.

Fig. 3. A three-dimensional schematic showing dimensions of the encounter-impact model components for (a) axial and (b) cross-flow turbines.

2.3. Model scenarios

In a simulated spatial domain, dimensions of model components are specified (Fig. 3a and 3b). Fish are released at the left border of the domain, providing them an opportunity to swim and aggregate before potentially encountering model components and the device. In periodic boundary conditions, fish are parameterized with a swimming velocity of 1 body length per second (15.5 cm) [11]. The simulated domain contains unidirectional flow (left to right) ranging from slack tide to 3.0 ms^{-1} , Admiralty Inlet's maximum tidal velocity [16]. In each simulation, behavioral aggregation parameters will be adjusted to influence patterns of grouping and movement among agents. The total number of time steps varies in each simulation run, as the model runs until fish are no longer in the model domain. Other than the turbine, model spatial volumes have no influence on fish trajectories and are only used in tabulating fish presence for probability calculations.

Probability of turbine detection and intensity of avoidance responses are influenced by the distance from the turbine. Fish reacting to the presence of tidal turbines have been observed at the reaction distance [12]. The probability of turbine detection by a fish in the ABM is inversely proportional to the distance from a turbine. If a fish detects the turbine once within the reaction radius of 140 m [12], then an avoidance response is triggered. The amplitude of the fish reaction behavior is inversely proportional to the distance from the turbine.

2.4. Probability calculations

Encounter and impact probabilities of fish with turbines are computed for individuals and populations to illustrate effects of fish behaviors on animal-device interactions. Probabilities of occurrence for each model component are estimated by tabulating fish duration (i.e., time steps) in each model component volume, and dividing by the duration of the simulation. Impact probabilities are estimated by tabulating the number of fish-turbine interactions, allocating the turbine upper section with entry and the lower portion of the turbine as collision. For fish that interact with a turbine, a value of 1 signifies collision with the lower section. For fish that enter the turbine upper section, blade strike probability is estimated using laboratory and field-based literature values [17], [18]. If a fish collides with the lower section of the turbine, followed by an entry into the upper section of a turbine, a collision and blade strike is possible. For population estimates, the sum of individuals in each model component is used to estimate population probabilities of occurrence within a model component and overall population impacts. Population occurrence probabilities are computed by quantifying the number of fish within each volume component and then dividing these counts by the total number of fish in the simulation.

3. Discussion

The agent-based, encounter-impact model estimates probabilities of encounter, collision, blade strike, and sequential collision and blade strike for both axial and cross-flow turbines. Scenarios will be used to set conditions for sets of simulation runs to derive probability distributions of scenario outcomes. As one scenario example, we predict that an increase in flow speed will lead to higher probabilities of collision and blade strike as tidal flow speeds can exceed fish swimming speeds [19], and fish being unable to avoid a turbine. We also predict that the formation of fish aggregations will reduce probability of impacts, as avoidance behavior of one fish in an aggregation can influence its neighbors to avoid the turbine. Trajectories of individual fish are likely to be variable, and probabilities of occurrence for any model component will depend, in part, on the sequence of events prior to any time step.

To date, there are few studies that utilize ABMs for MRE to quantify animal behavior and interaction rates in response to dynamic environmental conditions. One study that uses the HydroBoids ABM [10] to replicate the Collision Risk Model [9], revealed that approximately 1.1% of eels collided with a tidal turbine. Using scenarios, they investigated effects of animal speed, animal length, approach direction, and vertical migration on collision rates. Eichhorn *et al.*'s [20] ABM assessed collision risk of predatory birds with a wind turbine and found that collision risk declines as the distance between the animal and turbine increases. Goodwin *et al.* [21] used an Eulerian-Lagrangian-agent method to simulate fish behavior in response to varying flow conditions around a hydropower dam. They found that variation in fish behavior drives success of dam passage.

At this time, arbitrarily setting simulation parameter values for fish aggregation and avoidance rules is needed due to limited availability of Pacific herring aggregation and turbine avoidance empirical data. Obtaining relevant field data is essential to accurately quantify probabilities of occurrence and impact rates and to validate the ABM's

outcomes. Observations of individual fish encounters with turbines enable probability estimates of avoidance behaviors, collision events, and combined occurrences of collision followed by blade strike.

As for next steps, sensitivity analyses on model parameters will identify influential factors and parameters, and be used to identify what field data collections are needed [22]. By combining sensitivity analyses, simulation scenario runs, and ongoing data collection efforts, we seek to strengthen the model's accuracy and ensure its effectiveness in providing valuable insights for tidal energy site assessments and management strategies.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by a Department of Energy grant (DE-EE-0006816.0000) to the ALFA project with additional financial support of a Graduate Fellowship from the School of Aquatic and Fishery Sciences, University of Washington, Seattle, WA.

References

- [1] T. Castro-Santos and A. Haro, "Survival and Behavioral Effects of Exposure to a Hydrokinetic Turbine on Juvenile Atlantic Salmon and Adult American Shad," *Estuaries Coasts*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 203–214, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1007/s12237-013-9680-6. [Online].
- [2] K. E. Buenau, L. Garavelli, L. G. Hemery, and G. García Medina, "A Review of Modeling Approaches for Understanding and Monitoring the Environmental Effects of Marine Renewable Energy," *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 10, no. 1, Art. no. 1, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.3390/jmse10010094. [Online].
- [3] A. E. Copping, M. C. Freeman, A. M. Gorton, and L. G. Hemery, "Risk Retirement—Decreasing Uncertainty and Informing Consenting Processes for Marine Renewable Energy Development," *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 8, no. 3, Art. no. 3, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.3390/jmse8030172. [Online].
- [4] K. J. Murphy, S. Ciuti, and A. Kane, "An introduction to agent-based models as an accessible surrogate to field-based research and teaching," *Ecol. Evol.*, vol. 10, no. 22, pp. 12482–12498, 2020, doi: 10.1002/ece3.6848. [Online].
- [5] D. L. DeAngelis and W. M. Mooij, "Individual-Based Modeling of Ecological and Evolutionary Processes," *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Evol. Syst.*, vol. 36, pp. 147–168, 2005. doi: 10.1016/j.proenv.2012.01.134. [Online].
- [6] A. J. McLane, C. Semeniuk, G. J. McDermid, and D. J. Marceau, "The role of agent-based models in wildlife ecology and management," *Ecol. Model.*, vol. 222, no. 8, pp. 1544–1556, Apr. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2011.01.020. [Online].
- [7] L. An et al., "Challenges, tasks, and opportunities in modeling agent-based complex systems," *Ecol. Model.*, vol. 457, p. 109685, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2021.109685. [Online].
- [8] B. Wilson, R. Batty, F. Daunt, and C. Carter, "Collision risks between marine renewable energy devices and mammals, fish and diving birds. Report to the Scottish Executive," Jan. 2006. [Online]. Available: <https://tethys.pnnl.gov/publications/collision-risks-between-marine-renewable-energy-devices-mammals-fish-diving-birds>.
- [9] B. Band, C. Sparling, D. Thompson, J. Onoufriou, E. San Martin and N. West, "Refining estimates of collision risk for harbour seals and tidal turbines: Scottish Marine and Freshwater Science Vol 7 No 17," 2016, doi: 10.7489/1786-1, [Online].
- [10] K. Rossington and T. Benson, "An agent-based model to predict fish collisions with tidal stream turbines," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 151, pp. 1220–1229, May 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2019.11.127. [Online].

- [11] P. He, “Swimming speeds of marine fish in relation to fishing gears,” *ICES Mar Sci Symp*, vol. 196, pp. 183–189, Jan. 1993. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/284772904_Swimming_speeds_of_marine_fish_in_relation_to_fishing_gears.
- [12] H. Shen, G. B. Zydlewski, H. A. Viehman, and G. Staines, “Estimating the probability of fish encountering a marine hydrokinetic device,” *Renew. Energy*, vol. 97, pp. 746–756, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2016.06.026. [Online].
- [13] J. I. Peraza and J. K. Horne, “Quantifying conditional probabilities of fish-turbine encounters and impacts,” Manuscript Submitted for Publication, 2023.
- [14] D. A. Jacques, “Describing and Comparing Variability of Fish and Macrozooplankton Density at Marine Hydrokinetic Energy Sites,” Thesis, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://digital.lib.washington.edu/443/researchworks/handle/1773/27479>.
- [15] M. Bevelhimer, C. Scherelis, J. Colby, and M. A. Adonizio, “Hydroacoustic Assessment of Behavioral Responses by Fish Passing Near an Operating Tidal Turbine in the East River, New York,” *Trans. Am. Fish. Soc.*, vol. 146, no. 5, pp. 1028–1042, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.1080/00028487.2017.1339637. [Online].
- [16] J. K. Horne, D. A. Jacques, S. L. Parker-Stetter, H. L. Linder, and J. M. Nomura, “Evaluating Acoustic Technologies to Monitor Aquatic Organisms at Renewable Energy Sites Final Report,” U.S. Dept. of the Interior, Bureau of Ocean Energy Management, 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://espis.boem.gov/final%20reports/5415.pdf>
- [17] M. B. Courtney, A. J. Flanigan, M. Hostetter, and A. C. Seitz, “Characterizing Sockeye Salmon Smolt Interactions with a Hydrokinetic Turbine in the Kvichak River, Alaska,” *North Am. J. Fish. Manag.*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 1054–1065, 2022, doi: 10.1002/nafm.10806. [Online].
- [18] T. Yoshida et al., “Experimental study of fish behavior near a tidal turbine model under dark conditions,” *J. Mar. Sci. Technol.*, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s00773-021-00850-w. [Online].
- [19] A. Okubo, “Oceanic diffusion diagrams,” *Deep Sea Res. Oceanogr. Abstr.*, vol. 18, no. 8, pp. 789–802, Aug. 1971, doi: 10.1016/0011-7471(71)90046-5. [Online].
- [20] M. Eichhorn, K. Johst, R. Seppelt, and M. Drechsler, “Model-Based Estimation of Collision Risks of Predatory Birds with Wind Turbines,” *Ecol. Soc.*, vol. 17, no. 2, Apr. 2012, doi: 10.5751/ES-04594-170201. [Online].
- [21] R. A. Goodwin et al., “Fish navigation of large dams emerges from their modulation of flow field experience,” *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, vol. 111, no. 14, pp. 5277–5282, Apr. 2014, doi: 10.1073/pnas.1311874111. [Online].
- [22] H. Christopher Frey and S. R. Patil, “Identification and Review of Sensitivity Analysis Methods,” *Risk Anal.*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 553–578, 2002, doi: 10.1111/0272-4332.00039. [Online].